

Review

Strange Tales from a Chinese Studio: Book review

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Abstract: This paper is a book review for “The Strange Tales from a Chinese Studio”. The authors reviewed the plot the themes and the characters in the 104 stories collected in the book. The authors concluded that Pu Songling himself was the main character in this book and also agreed that “Strange” is the main theme of the book although morality, fate and supernatural are other themes brought out in this book. The authors also named their favourite character as Mr. Yin although he is not the main character and recommend people of all age groups to read the book for entertainment and moral guidance although young readers were recommended to do so under parental guidance to avoid some sexually explicit stories. The authors finally rated the book 5 stars.

Keywords: themes, plot, characters

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Name of reviewer	Chiremba Eunifer, Mamo Endalew Maru
Title of book	Strange Tales from a Chinese Studio
Author	Pu SongLing
Original title	“Liaozhai Zhiyi”
Original publication	1740
Language	Classical Chinese
Genre	Zhiguai; Chuanqi
English translation by	Sidney Sondergard
Publication Date:	2006
Publisher	Penguin Books

About the author

Pu Songling was a Chinese writer during the Qing dynasty and was best known as the author of Strange Tales from the Chinese Studio.

Plot

17th century, in the Qin dynasty. The plot of the stories in Strange Tales from a Chinese Studio vary widely as some are about ghosts while others are about magical creatures and others are about strange phenomena.

Themes Strange can be viewed as the major theme of this book. Morality, fate and supernatural other themes for the collections.

Main characters: the main character of this collection is Pu Songling himself as he is often portrayed as the observer of the strange events in the stories and often comments about them in a hilarious and satirical way. He sometimes appears as a character in the stories himself and is a figure of wisdom and insight.

Appearance

The feel of the book, at first sight is eye-catching and inviting. The book volume, its size and length were quite good and the font used not eye stretching which makes it perfect for bookworms. The text was quite readable and the illustrations were sceptical and a delight to look at. The font type selected leaves no room for improvements.

This book was about

This classical book is, first of all, a feast to the eyes, and can be best described in a single word, as "intriguing." "Strange Tales from a Chinese Studio" is a collection of 104 short stories by a Chinese writer, vividly narrated to keep the writer captivated while following for a stroll in the world of imagination. This Chinese writer may have lived in the 17th century as the tales relate. From the presentation of the stories, it can easily be concluded that the writer was setting the stories in his own era which could be anytime from 1640 to 1715 on the Anglo time scale. The writer more often than not uses ghosts, fox-spirits human spirits and several other varieties of demons. In his stories, these supernatural beings are interestingly coexisting with humans and often work towards the accomplishment of duties that would benefit humans. The scenes in these various stories take a conventional way as they all have a climax towards the end and always leave the reader still craving for more, wondering what could have happened next if fortune had turned the other way. The glossary also has interesting items on the concepts of interactions between these beings which are quite different from many African and Western base views.

The stories are quite strange and unbelievable, but quite good as they have some moral aspects that come from each of them. The settings are like the folktales of Africa in which animals would talk to each other like human beings, quarrelling, agreeing and at the end of the day making decisions, just like what human beings do. The fox-fairies, the ghosts and all the other strange and wandering spirits are all vigorously meting out rewards and punishments to either good or erring mortals respectively. This paranormal collection of tales based on popular legends and folklore of the day, were retold under the able penmanship of Pu Songling. The author poured out his love and care for his contemporaries and future fellow countrymen by telling and producing these strange tales.

The way one student a Mr Yin in one of the stories dined with the ghosts of the Shu family and witnessed their ghost daughter's wedding ceremony during the night (SongLing, 2006) is one aspect that makes the writer an awesome script-writer. The way the ghosts treated the student and the beautiful and handsome people wearing all kinds of ornate gowns, brings out the irony of the belief that ghosts are always haunting and tormenting human beings. Also like in many outcomes of these strange tales, the encounter stands as a base of the relationship that this particular student was going to have in the future with the heir of the Shu family in real world. The sarcastic ending of this story is in the proverb that was used as a concluding statement "...proves conclusively that although a fox may obtain a possession of a thing, even at a distance of many hundred miles, he will not venture to keep it together." Although Mr Yin had kept the goblet as a prized possession for a long time, he had to finally let it go to its rightful owner to keep a relationship. Just like the example cited, most of these stories are quite good, and equally many of them leave you flat and wondering "but how did it happen this way?" and "have I missed something here?" The answer to those questions will be "fate."

The book is overwhelmingly colourful with over a hundred pictures, one for each tale, and the illustrations describing its content in the best Chinese tradition. Most of the pictures depict typical Chinese setups in the 17th century in which

the script is set. The gardens with gnarled oak-trees and the plum-blossoms brings one home to the traditional Chinese castles and monasteries. The stories are written in such a captivating manner that after reading a single story, one finds him/herself looking forward to reading the next story every day. Even after a busy day's work, the book has an addiction effect which invites the reader to have a glance and without knowing, get engrossed and cannot put the book down until the strange story comes to its end. Without realising it, the reader finds him/herself having read more than a hundred stories and becoming familiarised with the old Chinese atmosphere. Without attending formal classes, the reader can easily gain an insight of the cultural beliefs, the landscapes, the marriage and courtship, and the capacities to know the future. Even the scary Chinese myths like their monsters, the occult traditions and their ghosts, are told in such an easy manner that they bring out all the fears yet still captivating the reader not to put the book down until he/she knows the verdict which usually counters the fears and brings a happy ending to the human beings.

Pu Songling managed to collect various weird and strange tales. Some of the strange stories are one-page-short, some are longer than twelve pages, and this makes the book quite readable for people who are busybodies. One can read one story from introduction to conclusion in between tasks and without realising get to finish the whole book. The Chinese beliefs of the wise snakes, mice and birds and their capacities of knowing the future in advance are all well illustrated in this book. Furthermore, the reality of their ghosts, as the writer insists, begins to dawn on the mind of the reader as he/she progresses with the text. The spirit of the foxes coming mainly as beautiful young ladies bring out moral discipline to young suitors after reading this book, one begins to tread cautiously in love affairs and allow the elders to make choices which is typical of Chinese marriages. The deceased young people coming back to life in their own bodies or the recently dead bodies reduce the fear of death at the anticipation of being able to re-join the living again.

The majority of the tales revolve around fox-spirits or ghosts which are able to take any form including the form of humans. The foxes are mostly malicious, using humans to create magical transformations to further their own goals of eternal life, but some can be trustworthy, respectful, kind and sympathetic to the humans around them. These tales, are a reflection of the fantasies of the Qing men in that era as well over half of them are sexual. It must have been every Qing man's dream to have beautiful young women suddenly walk into your bedroom and sleep with you. In most of the tales, the foxes -spirits and ghosts try to get along with a bunch of selfish and stupid humans.

What makes the reading more interesting and dumbfounding is that the writer described his tales as stories accumulated from his neighbours, relatives and friends, and not work of fiction. This reality then makes the reader want to explore more about the Chinese tradition and culture through the eyes of the writer. Reading this book feels like one is eavesdropping the conversations of ancient Chinese folks or better still reading a diary of news reporter of that era. The strange romance, the strange cultures and the breath-taking bizarre moments, all left me craving for more. I personally do not like reading large volumes, but these 104 strange tales, in the 450 pages were like a pamphlet, I couldn't stop asking for more, but as the writer decided, the book had to come to an end.

Our favourite character in the book

Our favourite character in this whole book was Mr. Yin, a very dumb but cool character. The stupidity he portrayed in risking his life for a mere luncheon and later again risked by stealing from the ghosts in order to prove a point to his friends, is typical to the kind of people the foxes targeted.

What we liked about the book:

The book, *Strange Tales from a Chinese Studio*, is great. The author starts off with an Introduction, then all the stories, and at the end there is an Author's Foreword. The Author's Foreword, has an extensive Glossary, and similarly extensive Notes on every single story. For students studying literature and those that want a deeper understanding of the Chinese culture, its actually great news.

Another credit for this book is the great translation. The book was translated from Chinese to English without losing that Chinese taste and atmosphere. The stories are interesting, informative and carry a lot of moral value. For a casual reader, the entertainment is amazingly well orchestrated and gives value for the reader's money. The reader gets fascinated in the in strange stories while at the same time learning a lot about the Chinese culture in a less stressful way. For foreign students studying in China, the book is perfect. The writer's ability to dodge monotony and being unpredictable deserves five-star rating and is something to smile about. The weird demons that wear the skin of beautiful women in order to lure men to their death in one story are never the same in the next story as, the same spirits try everything in their power to rescue or to benefit human beings. The writer's ability to keep the reader guessing, unsure, yet eager to know the next text is very appraisable. There are also a good deal of footnotes explaining cultural background to each story which makes it easy for the reader to figure out the direction of the stories.

What we did not like about the book:

The fairy tales are made to seem real by the writer, this might lead young readers to crave for experiments especially with the number of sexual themes in most of the stories. Parents are therefore warned that most of the tales explicitly display sexual enticement, and would not be appropriate for children. Initially, the Strange Tales from the Chinese Studio starts off without so many fox stories, and then as the reader becomes entangled, almost every story has a fox, which can get predictable. The historic aspect and the scholastic explanations take up most of the book and are generally unneeded to understand the stories as there are a lot of footnotes for most of the work and tales.

Reviewers' opinion:

In our opinion, some publisher could re-issue this English translation and commission an artist to convey the atmosphere of the stories, especially those semi-erotic love-making passages

Recommended readers:

Readers of all other ages will be enthralled by these tales. I however highly recommend this book to use with parental guidance for little children to skip the semi-erotic love-making passages.

our rating for this book:

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